

Synthesis in the Pyrazolone Series. Action of Thiosemi- carbazine and Semicarbazine on Ketonic Esters. Part II.

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In a previous communication (*This Journal*, 1926, **3**, 30) it has been shown by one of us that thiosemicarbazide and semicarbazide can condense with acetoacetic ester to form pyrazolone derivatives, the reaction of course taking place in two distinct phases. In the first phase of the reaction a hydrazone is formed which in the second phase parts with a molecule of alcohol to yield the pyrazolone.

In the present paper our object is to study the behaviour of thiosemicarbazide and semicarbazide and their 4-substitution products on benzoylactic ester and diacetosuccinic ester and to see whether it is possible to obtain pyrazolones from them also. As the result of our investigation it is found that the carbazides can be made to react with the ketonic esters to give pyrazolones. But one peculiarity to be noticed here is that while thiosemicarbazide gives with acetoacetic ester a hydrazone, such a compound could not be prepared by the authors from 4-substituted thiosemicarbazides and the ester. This is probably due to the fact that these substances show no tendency to react with the ketonic esters at the ordinary temperature but on heating the two components together in presence of alcohol they combine to yield pyrazolones, the intermediate hydrazones not being possible to isolate. Another interesting fact is that whereas acetoacetic ester combines with semi- and thiosemi-carbazides to form hydrazones, the benzoylactic or diacetosuccinic ester shows no tendency to form such hydrazones with these components although the reaction proceeds at the ordinary temperature yielding the pyrazolone compounds. For example, benzoylactic ester and semicarbazide give 3-phenylpyrazolone-1-carbamide (I) according to the following scheme :

Similarly diacetosuccinic ester should react with semicarbazide in two different ways to yield pyrazolone derivatives with the elimination of water and alcohol. From one molecule of the ester and one of semicarbazide, a 3-methylpyrazolone-1-carbamide-4-acetoacetic ester (II) may result, thus:

This compound may then react with a second molecule of semicarbazide to give rise to a 4-bis-3-methylpyrazolone-1-carbamide (III), a compound which can also be derived from one molecule of the ester and two of semicarbazide. But by taking molecular proportions of the components a compound of formula (II) could not be prepared, the product always being the bis-pyrazolone. The reaction, therefore, proceeds according to the equation:

In the previous communication 3-methylpyrazolone-1-carbamide has been shown to be stable only in the cold as the carbamide group is very easily eliminated from this compound even by gentle warming with alcohol with the formation of 3-methylpyrazolone, a compound easily obtainable from acetoacetic ester and hydrazine hydrate. 3-Phenylpyrazolone 1-carbamide and 4-bis-3-methylpyrazolone-1-carbamide, on the contrary, are comparatively stable substances as

they do not part with the carbamide group even on prolonged boiling either with water or alcohol. 3-Phenylpyrazolone can, however, be obtained from 3-phenylpyrazolone-1 carbamide by heating the latter with alcoholic hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube. Bis-3-methylpyrazolone can be easily obtained from 4-bis-3-methylpyrazolone-1-carbamide by heating the latter at its melting point when it parts with the carbamide group.

It has also been shown that 3-methylpyrazolone-1-carbamide (or thiocarbamide) can react with a second molecule of acetoacetic ester to yield 3-methylpyrazolone-1-carbonyl-(or thiocarbonyl)- β -uramidocrotonic ester. But the pyrazolones derived from the interaction of benzoylactic ester on semicarbazide and thiosemicarbazide as well as those derived from diacetosuccinic ester and the carbazides could not be made to react with a second molecule of acetoacetic or benzoylactic ester.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of Benzoylactic Ester with Thiosemicarbazide and its Substitution Products.

3-Phenylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbamide.—This compound was obtained when thiosemicarbazide hydrochloride and benzoylactic ester were allowed to react in presence of sodium acetate: The ester (1 mol.) dissolved in alcohol was added to an aqueous solution of the hydrochloride of the base (1 mol.). After shaking the mixture for some time sodium acetate (1 mol.) was added and the mixture allowed to stand for two days. The solid crystalline product that separated out was filtered, washed with water, and crystallised from alcohol in white rectangles, m.p. 161°. (Found: N, 19.30. $C_{10}H_8ON_3S$ requires N, 19.18 per cent.).

The same compound was obtained much more easily by heating an alcoholic solution of benzoylactic ester (1 mol.) with the carbazide hydrochloride (1 mol.) in the least quantity of aqueous sodium acetate solution. The pyrazolone so obtained is insoluble in ether, benzene and chloroform; slightly soluble in cold but easily so in hot alcohol.

4: 4'-Dibromo-3-phenylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbamide was prepared by allowing an excess of bromine in acetic acid solution to react on 3-phenylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbamide suspended in the solvent. As

the reaction began with evolution of heat, the pyrazolone gradually went into solution and torrents of hydrobromic acid fumes were evolved. After stirring for some time a small quantity of the dibromoderivative separated as a red crystalline product. A further quantity was obtained by diluting the acetic acid solution with water. It was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in light orange-red microscopic crystals, which begin to shrink at 130° with the slow liberation of bromine. (Found: S, 8.83; Br, 42.65. $C_{10}H_7ON_2SBr_2$ requires S, 8.48; Br, 42.44 per cent.).

4-iso-Nitroso-3-phenylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbamide.—It was obtained by adding sodium nitrite solution to the pyrazolone suspended in acetic acid. The reaction began with the separation of a yellow crystalline product. This was collected, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 174°. (Found: N, 22.70. $C_{10}H_8O_2N_4S$ requires N, 22.58 per cent.).

The isonitroso compound has a strong acid reaction. It dissolves in alkali and from the alkaline solution it separates unchanged on acidification.

3-Phenylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbophenylamide was prepared from a mixture of equimolecular proportions of 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide and the ketonic ester in alcoholic solution. After heating for about three hours the solution was allowed to cool when the pyrazolone separated as white crystals, a further quantity being obtainable by adding water to the mother-liquor. The product crystallised from dilute alcohol in white long rectangles, m.p. 127°. (Found: N, 14.46. $C_{16}H_{18}ON_3S$ requires N, 14.24 per cent.).

3-Phenylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbo-p-tolylamide.—It was obtained from molecular proportions of 4-p-tolylthiosemicarbazide and the ketonic ester in alcoholic solution. On concentrating the solution and allowing it to stand with frequent scratching and shaking the pyrazolone was obtained as a white crystalline mass. This was filtered and then recrystallised from dilute alcohol in white rectangles, m.p. 106°. (Found: N, 13.77. $C_{17}H_{18}ON_3S$ requires N, 13.59 per cent.).

3-Phenylpyrazolone-1-thiocarboethylamide.—It was obtained by heating an alcoholic solution of 4-ethylthiosemicarbazide and the ester in molecular proportions. On allowing the cold solution to stand crystals gradually came out and after two days these were collected and crystallised from dilute alcohol in

white rectangles, m.p. 136°. (Found : N, 16.78. $C_{11}H_{11}ONS$ requires N, 17.00 per cent.).

Codensation of Benzoyl-acetic ester with Semicarbazide.

3-Phenylpyrazolone-1-carbamide.—This compound was prepared in the same way as the corresponding thio-compound by taking molecular proportions of the reactants. An aqueous solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride and sodium acetate was added to the ketonic ester diluted with alcohol and the mixture was vigorously shaken. After a short time a white crystalline precipitate was obtained. This was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 179°. (Found : N, 20.78. $C_{10}H_9O_2N_3$ requires N, 20.69 per cent.).

The same compound was also obtained by heating an alcoholic solution of the components. It is sparingly soluble in cold but easily so in hot alcohol; insoluble in ether, benzene and chloroform. The carbamide group is not easily eliminated from this compound but on heating with alcoholic hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube at 120°-130° for several hours this group can be removed with difficulty and the hydrochloride of 3-phenylpyrazolone is formed from which by neutralisation with ammonia, the free base is obtained; m.p. 236°, identical with the compound of Curtius (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1894, 50, 515).

4:4'-Dibromo-3-phenylpyrazolone-1-carbamide.—It was obtained from an excess of bromine and the pyrazolone in acetic acid solution. During the addition of bromine great heat was evolved and hydrobromic acid fumes were produced. After some time the dibromo compound separated from the solution. This was filtered and crystallised from acetic acid; m.p. 144°. (Found : Br, 44.20. $C_{10}H_7O_2N_3Br_2$ requires Br 44.32 per cent.).

4-isoNitroso-3-phenylpyrazolone-1-carbamide.—It was prepared from the solution of the pyrazolone in acetic acid to which an aqueous solution of sodium nitrite was slowly added. The isonitroso compound separated at once as yellow crystals. This was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from alcohol; m. p. 204°. (Found : N, 24.29. $C_{10}H_9O_3N_4$ requires N, 24.13 per cent.).

*Condensation of Diacetosuccinic ester with Semicarbazide :
Formation of 4-Bis-3-methylpyrazolone-1-carbamide :*

To a solution of the ester (1 mol.) in alcohol was added a solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride (2 mols) in aqueous sodium acetate solution. The reaction began with evolution of heat and separation of the pyrazolone crystals. The mixture was then heated on the water-bath for 10-15 minutes to bring the reaction to an end. The crystals were filtered from the solution, washed with water and recrystallised from alcohol; m.p. 128°. (Found : N, 30·15. $C_{10}H_{14}O_4N_6$ requires N, 30·00 per cent.).

At its melting point it is at once converted into bis-3-methylpyrazolone with the elimination of the carbamide groups. The pyrazolone so obtained after crystallisation from water begins to turn brown at 255° and melts at 290°. (Found : N, 28·34. $C_8H_{10}O_2N_4$ requires N, 28·86 per cent.).

Condensation of Diacetosuccinic Ester with Thiosemicarbazides.

4-Bis-3-methylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbamide.—It was prepared from thiosemicarbazide (1 mol.) and the ester (1 mol.) using alcohol as solvent. After heating for some time a clear solution was obtained. The filtrate on cooling was filled with crystals. This was recrystallised from alcohol in white rectangles, m.p. 197°. (Found : N, 27·15. $C_{10}H_{12}O_2N_4S_2$ requires N, 26·92 per cent.).

4-Bis-3-methylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbonylamide.

It was obtained as before from 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (2 mols.) and the ester (1 mol.). This was crystallised from alcohol in white long rectangles, m.p. 191°. (Found : N, 18·22. $C_{22}H_{20}O_2N_6S_2$ requires N, 18·10 per cent.).

4-Bis-3-methylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbo-p-tolylamide.—It was obtained from 4-p-tolythiosemicarbazide (2 mols.) and the ester (1 mol.). The pyrazolone was recrystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 201°-202°. (Found : N, 17·25. $C_{24}H_{24}O_2N_6S_2$ requires N, 17·07 per cent.).

4-Bis-3-methylpyrazolone-1-thiocarboethylamide.—It was obtained from 4-ethylthiosemicarbazide (2 mols.) and the ester (1 mol.) in alcoholic solution. The pyrazolone separated from the solution on long standing in white rectangles, m.p. 191°. (Found : N, 22·98. $C_{14}H_{20}O_2N_6S_2$ requires N, 22·82 per cent.).

Condensation of Acetoacetic Ester with Substituted Thiosemicarbasides.

3-Methylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbophenylamide.—It was obtained from 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide and acetoacetic ester in alcoholic solution. The mixture was heated for about two hours and the solution allowed to cool when crystals separated out. This was recrystallised from alcohol in white rectangles, m.p. 117°. (Found : N, 18·20. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_3S$ requires N, 18·02 per cent.).

3-Methylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbo-p-tolylamide was prepared by heating an alcoholic solution of 4-p-tolylthiosemicarbazide and the ketonic ester. The compound separated on long standing. This was crystallised from dilute alcohol in white rectangles, m.p. 121°. (Found : N, 17·21. $C_{11}H_{13}ON_3S$ requires N, 17·00 per cent.).

3-Methylpyrazolone-1-thiocarbomethylamide.—By heating for about for two hours an alcoholic solution of 4-methylthiosemicarbazide and the ketonic ester and concentrating the solution and allowing to stand crystals made their appearance after two days. This was crystallised from dilute alcohol ; m.p. 84°. (Found : N, 24·75. $C_6H_8ON_3S$ requires N, 24·56 per cent.).

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